

Deliverable 4.2 - API documentation

EURAKNOS

Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs towards a European Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Open Source System

Task 4.2: Design and development of a prototype e-KRP

Summary

Task description: Based on the consultations and the work performed in WPs 2 and 3, a prototype e-KRP will be designed and developed to allow access to a centralised data repository, where data from the KR of existing TNs will be stored. An API authentication mechanism has been developed, which allows any interested party/agent (human or machine) to access the data objects stored in the e-KRP. The present report describes the outcome of the activity of Task 4.2 related to the API of EURAKNOS. Specifically, it provides the documentation of the API together with the description of the technologies used for its development. Additionally, it presents the API calls for the retrieval and deletion of the data objects from the e-KRP.

Results and conclusion: The EURAKNOS API and the respective documentation.

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Lead Beneficiary	Deliverable Author(S)		
Agricultural University of Athens (AUA)	Sofia Mouseti (AUA)		
Beneficiaries	Deliverable Co-Author (S)		
Leap Forward Group (LFG) AKI Nonprofit KFT (AKI) Innovation for Agriculture (IfA)	Philip Verbist (LFG) Hercules Panoutsopoulos (AUA) Spyros Fountas (AUA)		
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List of abbreviations and acronyms

API – Application Programming Interface

CRUD – Create, Read, Update, Delete

EURAKNOS – Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs: towards a European Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Open Source System

HTML – Hyper Text Markup Language

HTTP – Hyper Text Transfer Protocol

IAM – Identity and Access Management

IT – Information technologies

JSON – JavaScript Object Notation

JVM – Java Virtual Machine

OAS - OpenAPI Specification

REST – Representational state transfer

RMI – Remote Method Invocation

RPC – Remote Procedure Call

SMTP – Simple Mail Transfer Protocol

SOAP – Simple Object Access Protocol

TCP – Transmission Control Protocol

UI – User Interface

URI – Uniform Resource Identifier

WSDL - Web Services Definition Language

XML – eXtensible Markup Language

1. Introduction

This report provides the documentation of the EURAKNOS API (Application Programming Interface); i.e., the mechanism built to enable third-party entities (namely, human and/or machine agents) access and consume the data available in the EURAKNOS e-KRP data repository. As Mestre (2018) points out, the documentation of an API serves the purpose of “*a manual containing all the information required to work with the API, with details about the functions, classes, return types, arguments and more.*” Based on that, there are several benefits from the development and supply of API documentations to the community. Specifically, the documentation helps improve the experience of developers using the API by significantly reducing the amount of time required to be spent on understanding how it works and deciphering unexpected errors when using it. The API users can easily take advantage of it and be productive without needing to depend upon an expert (having the API-related knowledge) who would have to spend time explaining how the API has been designed and functions. In addition, the API documentation facilitates the adoption of best practices with respect to product maintenance and updates.

Given the benefits of having and providing documentation for an API, the present deliverable report has the aim of making available the details about the EURAKNOS API. The work that was required for the development of the EURAKNOS API was technical in nature. For that reason, the expertise that was needed for its development could be provided only by the partners with a technical profile and know-how. In any case, the API development has been one specific activity within the context of Task 4.2, in which (i.e., Task 4.2) all the involved (according to the GA) partners have had a role and contribution. The API has been developed as the result of the work of UGent (more specifically, IT developers of the University of Ghent) under the coordination and supervision of AUA. AKI has provided its support and feedback at the early stages of the process. The contribution of Maastricht University (MU) should be also mentioned. MU has not been involved in EURAKNOS as a direct partner; yet, it has contributed to the API development, and to the technical activities undertaken in Task 4.2 in general, given the leading role it has in EUREKA (i.e., the follow-up project of EURAKNOS).

Before proceeding to the API documentation (Section 3), the report starts with the outline of necessary information about what an API actually is, how it works, and the different types of APIs that exist. This background information is provided in Section 2 with the aim to help the reader develop the necessary background knowledge and establish an understanding of what an API is and needed for. In the context of explaining what an API is, widely used API categories and architecture types are presented in detail. The results of the comparison of the two major API types (i.e., the REST and SOAP APIs), relating to the architecture styles employed, are presented as part of the API-related discussion. The report concludes with a summary of its key points and references to the steps intended to be taken for the API’s further development.

2. Background

The purpose of this section of the deliverable report is to provide background information about what an API (Application Programming Interface) is, how it actually works, as well as the types of APIs that exist. The intention is not to use a difficult to comprehend technical terminology, but rather help the reader frame an API-related theoretical background by making use of an easy-to-understand language.

2.1. Overview of what and Application Programming Interface is and used for

2.1.1. What an Application Programming Interface is

An Application Programming Interface (API) is the interface that a software program presents to other programs, to humans, and, in the case of web APIs, to the world via the Internet. APIs are the building blocks of the interoperability among major business platforms in the web. An API is essentially a set of rules that determine how computers, applications, or machines can talk to each other. A typical user

interface is intended to be used by humans, whereas APIs are intended to be used by machine agents (i.e., an application or a computer system). Some examples of API-based interactions include a cloud application communicating with a server, servers pinging each other, or applications interacting with an operating system.

APIs have emerged out of the need to exchange information with providers of data who are equipped to solve specific problems, so developers at other companies or organisations do not have to devote time solving those problems themselves. It can be considered as a software intermediary that allows two applications to talk to each other. In other words, an API is the messenger that delivers our request to the provider, from which we request something, and then delivers the response back to us. It defines functionalities that are independent of their respective implementations, which in turn allows those implementations and definitions to vary without compromising each other. Thus, a good API makes it easier to develop software by providing the building blocks. APIs enable developers to make repetitive yet complex processes highly reusable with a bit of code. The speed at which APIs allow developers to build applications is crucial given the current pace of application development.

It is important to note that while web APIs are the most common ones, they are not however limited to the web. There are indeed APIs for virtually every machine or system expected to interact with other machines or systems. When an API is created for a specific technology, it is easier for others to use this technology in their products and services. This is the reason why APIs have fundamentally transformed the way in which software developers create their applications. APIs have introduced an entirely new vertical of a “platform-as-a-service” software to companies. API-based tools are the reason why data integrations between essential business software are possible.

Point-to-point integration has been the traditional approach in which software developers wrote custom integration code, directly within an application, rather than using an integration broker. Adding integration code directly in an application created tight coupling which led to a web of interdependent systems. Modifying tightly coupled applications needed significant investments in time and resources. Application Programming Interfaces have emerged as a means to enable reuse and provide access to external services. APIs provide new functionalities that organisations and businesses can bring into their applications to create better user experience. Moreover, they allow to decouple complex systems through simple API interfaces and allow other users to consume them. APIs provide a new level of interactivity and a better way for developers to consume and use services behind a well-defined interface.

A major advantage of APIs is that they allow the abstraction of functionality between one system and another. An API endpoint decouples the consuming application from the infrastructure that provides a service (see Figure 1). Changes to the infrastructure behind the endpoint should not be noticed by the applications relying on the API, provided that what the service provider delivers remains unchanged. The ability of API-driven connectivity to allow systems to change as easily as plugging in a plug to a socket is key to the modern vision of enterprise IT.

Figure 1. APIs allow the decoupling of an application from the infrastructure that serves the application. This way, multiple and diverse applications can be plugged-in to the API and have access to the same service.

For an API developer, it is important to understand who the API users are (e.g., other developers), what their needs are, and the purposes they are going to use the API for. Focusing on developers prevents an API developer from building APIs that no one wants to use or that do not fit the usage requirements of developers. Changing an API’s design can be quite difficult and the cost of switching from one API design to another is high for most developers. Thus, it is important to specify and validate the API long before the beginning of its implementation.

2.1.2. How does an Application Programming Interface work?

Data is typically stored in a database that is hosted in a physical server. To retrieve data, the interested party needs to know how to talk to that database in order to get what he/she wants. The simplest way to describe an API is as a user interface (UI) that applications, databases, and devices can exploit to programmatically exchange data with one another. An API facilitates the process by receiving requests and responding with the data needed for some functionality or service. Most web APIs are located between the application and the web server. The API is the intermediary between the application and the web server, and the API call is the request. The user initiates an API call that tells the application to do something. Then, the application uses an API to ask the web server to do something in response. Some characteristic examples are the following:

- When a user types a URL into the browser to visit a webpage, he/she is sending a request to a server for all the data needed to display that webpage.
- When a user clicks the “play” button to start streaming video content, a request is sent to a server to access a video file and start playing its content.

An example of how an API works is illustrated in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2. An example of a REST API, one of the most prominent architectures used in web-related technologies.

2.2. Types of Application Programming Interfaces

2.2.1. Open APIs

The APIs of this type are also known as public APIs. There are no restrictions in accessing APIs of this type, because they are publicly available. They are openly available to developers and other users with minimal restrictions. They may require registration (i.e., the use of an API Key or OAuth¹) or they may be completely open. They focus on external users (e.g., software developers) to enable them to access data or services.

2.2.2. Web APIs

Web APIs are APIs that can be accessed using the HTTP protocol². The API defines endpoints and valid request and response formats. Web APIs include the APIs used to communicate with the browser. They

¹ OAuth 2.0 is the industry-standard protocol for authorization. OAuth 2.0 focuses on client developer simplicity while providing specific authorization flows for web applications, desktop applications, mobile phones, and living room devices. This specification and its extensions are being developed within the [IETF OAuth Working Group](https://oauth.net/2/). (source: <https://oauth.net/2/>).

² HTTP is a protocol which allows the fetching of resources, such as HTML documents. It is the foundation of any data exchange on the Web and it is a client-server protocol, which means requests are initiated by the recipient, usually the Web browser. A complete document is reconstructed from the different sub-documents fetched, for instance text, layout description, images, videos, scripts, and more. (source: <https://developer.mozilla.org/en-US/docs/Web/HTTP/Overview>).

may be services such as web notifications and web storage. Different web APIs feature varying levels of security and privacy including open, internal, and partner APIs. Multiple web APIs can be combined into a composite API (i.e., a collection of data or service APIs).

2.2.3. Partner APIs

A developer needs specific rights to access this type of API because it is not publicly available. Partner APIs are APIs exposed by/to strategic business partners. They are not available to the public and need specific authorisation to access them. Just like open APIs, partner APIs are the top of the iceberg given that they are the most visible ones, used to communicate beyond the boundaries of a company. They are usually exposed to a public API developer portal that developers can access in a self-service mode. While open APIs are completely open, there is an on-boarding process with a specific validation workflow to get access to partner APIs. Partner APIs are technically similar to open APIs, but they feature restricted access, often controlled through a third-party API gateway. They are usually used for a specific purpose such as providing access to a paid-for service. This is a very common pattern in the “software-as-a-service” ecosystem.

2.2.4. Internal APIs

They are also known as private APIs. Only internal systems expose this type of API. These are usually designed for internal use within a company. The company uses this type of API among its different internal teams to facilitate the improvement of products and services. Internal APIs are hidden from external users and are only exposed by internal systems. Internal APIs are not meant for consumption outside the company but rather for use across different internal development teams for productivity improvement and reuse of services. A good governance process is to expose them to an internal API developer portal that connects to the internal Identity and Access Management³ (IAM) systems to authenticate and allow users to access the right set of APIs. Using internal APIs has several advantages over conventional integration techniques, including security and access control, an audit trail of system access, and a standard interface for connecting multiple services.

2.2.1. Composite APIs

This type of API combines different data and service APIs. It comprises a sequence of tasks that run synchronously as a result of the execution and not at the request of a task. Its main uses are to speed up the process of execution and improve the performance of the listeners in the web interfaces. They are built using the API orchestration capabilities of an API creation tool. They allow developers to access several endpoints in one call. Composite APIs are useful, for example, in a microservices architecture pattern where one needs information from several services to perform a single task. These could be different endpoints of a single API, or they could be multiple services or data sources. Using composite APIs can reduce server load and improve application performance, as one call can return all the data that a user needs.

A categorisation of APIs according to the access rights granted to external audiences is shown in Figure 3 below.

³ Identity and access management (IAM) in enterprise IT is about defining and managing the roles and access privileges of individual network users and the circumstances in which users are granted (or denied) those privileges.

Who uses the API?	External Access	App Types	Examples
Internal Developers (Internal API)		B2E, A2A B2B, B2C,	
Partner / Customer Developers (Partner, Customer API)		B2B, B2C	
Developers Anywhere (Open API)	Google Maps		

Figure 3. The major types of Application Programming Interfaces in terms of access rights to external audiences.

2.3. Types of Application Programming Interface architectural styles

Another area of choice regarding an API relates to which API architectural style(s) can be employed. It is indeed critical to select an architectural style or pattern that best fits the intended use of the API, especially if certain functional capabilities are needed. This tends to be an API design-related decision that is made by more technically-inclined teams. Before making this decision, it is essential to have a basic understanding of what infrastructure is already in place (whether the systems are on-premise or cloud-based, which systems and datasets are needed to be used, what security protocols need to be implemented, and what functionalities are required). In the spirit of API-first design, the desired functionality and user experiences should inform changes to the legacy IT estate rather than allowing the status quo of the legacy IT estate to dictate functionality or experience.

There are various architecture-related styles for APIs, as well as varying data formats in these styles. The most common ones are listed below.

2.3.1. REST APIs

REST⁴ ([Representational State Transfer](#)) is an architectural style of web services that work as a channel of communication between different computers or systems connected to the Internet. The APIs that are backed by the architectural style of the REST architectural system are called REST APIs. REST API compliant web services, database systems, and computer systems permit requesting systems to get robust access and redefine representations of web-based resources by deploying a predefined set of stateless protocols and standard operations. By these protocols and operations and by redeploying the manageable and updatable components without causing the effect on the system, REST API systems deliver fast performance, reliability, and more progression. A REST API has the following features:

- **Stateless** - A REST API is stateless in nature. REST APIs do not allow the server (or the receiving end) to retain the information they receive from the client/sender. The client sends information to the server in packets that the server can understand in isolation (without context from past packets).

⁴ Roy Fielding defined REST in his 2000 PhD dissertation "Architectural Styles and the Design of Network-based Software Architectures" at UC Irvine.

- **Uniform Interface** - A client and a server should communicate through HTTP (HyperText Transfer Protocol) using URIs (Unique Resource Identifiers), CRUD (Create, Read, Update, Delete), and JSON (JavaScript Object Notation)⁵ conventions.
- **Client-Server** - The client and the server should be independent of each other. The changes made on the server side should not affect the client side and vice versa. This is the so called “separation of concerns” and enables each side to grow and scale on its own without needing (or affecting) the other one.
- **Cache** - The client should cache the responses as this improves the user experience by making them faster and more efficient. The client side of a REST API should have the ability to cache or store information for a certain period of time. This reduces the number of times the application needs to call on the API and thus, reduces server usage and saves resources. Caching also enables developers to improve the user experience of their applications by making them faster and more efficient.
- **Layered** - The API should support a layered architecture with each layer contributing to a clear hierarchy. Each layer should be loosely coupled and allow for encapsulation. The REST API should use different architecture layers, each contributing towards a clear hierarchy. Each layer is loosely coupled, which lets you encapsulate legacy code in one part of the API, while changing another part of the API to a new technology.
- **Code on Demand** - Code on Demand is an optional rule. It allows you to transmit code within an application through the API. However, given the fact that modern web APIs use multiple languages, Code on Demand has not been widely implemented due to security and efficiency risks.

A RESTful web service **request** contains:

- **An Endpoint URL** - An application implementing a RESTful API will define one or more URL endpoints with a domain, port, path, and/or query string; for example, <https://mydomain/user/123?format=json>.
- **The HTTP method** - HTTP defines a set of request methods to indicate the desired action to be performed for a given resource. Although they can also be nouns, these request methods are sometimes referred to as HTTP verbs. Each of them incorporates a different semantic, but some common features are shared by a group of them; e.g., a request method can be safe, idempotent, or cacheable. Different HTTP methods, mapping to application create, read, update, and delete (CRUD) operations, can be used on any endpoint. All the available HTTP methods are listed in Table 1 below.

Table 1. The available HTTP methods ([source](#))

HTTP method	HTTP method description
GET	The GET method requests a representation of the specified resource. Requests using GET should only retrieve data.
HEAD	The HEAD method asks for a response identical to that of a GET request, but without the response body.
POST	The POST method is used to submit an entity to the specified resource, often causing a change in state or side effects on the server.
PUT	The PUT method replaces all current representations of the target resource with the request payload.
DELETE	The DELETE method deletes the specified resource.

⁵ JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) is a lightweight data-interchange format. It is easy for humans to read and write. It is easy for machines to parse and generate. It is based on a subset of the JavaScript Programming Language Standard ECMA-262 (3rd Edition - December 1999). JSON is a text format that is completely language independent but uses conventions familiar to programmers of the C-family of languages (C, C++, C#, Java, JavaScript, Perl, Python, and many others). These properties make JSON an ideal data-interchange language. ([source: https://www.json.org/json-en.html](https://www.json.org/json-en.html)).

CONNECT	The CONNECT method establishes a tunnel to the server identified by the target resource.
OPTIONS	The OPTIONS method is used to describe the communication options for the target resource.
TRACE	The TRACE method performs a message loop-back test along the path to the target resource.
PATCH	The PATCH method is used to apply partial modifications to a resource.

Examples of HTTP methods:

- a GET request to `/user/` returns a list of registered users on a system.
- a POST request to `/user/123` creates a user with the ID `123` using the body data.
- a PUT request to `/user/123` updates user `123` with the body data.
- a GET request to `/user/123` returns the details of user `123`.
- a DELETE request to `/user/123` deletes user `123`.
- **HTTP headers** - HTTP headers let the client and the server pass additional information with an HTTP request or response. An HTTP header consists of its case-insensitive name followed by a colon (":") and then by its value. Information such as authentication tokens or cookies can be contained in the HTTP request header. Based on their contexts, headers can be grouped as follows:
 - General headers apply to both requests and responses, but with no relation to the data transmitted in the body.
 - Request headers contain more information about the resource to be fetched, or about the client requesting the resource.
 - Response headers hold additional information about the response like its location, or about the server providing it.
 - Entity headers contain information about the body of the resource like its content length, or MIME type.
- **Body Data** - Data is normally transmitted in the HTTP body in a way that is identical to the HTML `<form>` submissions, or by sending a single JSON-encoded data string.
- **REST API Response** - The response payload can be whatever is practical, namely data, HTML, an image, an audio file, and so on. Data responses are typically JSON-encoded; however, XML, CSV, simple strings, or any other format can be used. You could allow the return format to be specified in the request; for example: `"/user/123?format=json"` or `"/user/123?format=xml"`. An appropriate HTTP status code should also be set in the response header. "200 OK" is the status code most often used for successful requests. However, the code "201 Created" may also be returned when a record is created. Errors should return an appropriate code such as "400 Bad Request", "404 Not Found", "401 Unauthorized", and so on. Response status codes are part of the HTTP specification. There are quite a number of them to address the most common situations. In the spirit of having our RESTful services embrace the HTTP specification, web APIs should return relevant HTTP status codes. For example, when a resource is successfully created (e.g., from a POST request), the API should return the HTTP status code 201. A list of valid HTTP status codes is shown in Figure 4 below.

1xx Informational

100 Continue

2xx Success

★ 200 OK
 203 Non-Authoritative Information
 206 Partial Content
 226 IM Used

3xx Redirection

300 Multiple Choices
 303 See Other
 306 (Unused)

4xx Client Error

★ 400 Bad Request
 ★ 403 Forbidden
 406 Not Acceptable
 ★ 409 Conflict
 412 Precondition Failed
 415 Unsupported Media Type
 418 I'm a teapot (RFC 2324)
 423 Locked (WebDAV)
 426 Upgrade Required
 431 Request Header Fields Too Large
 450 Blocked by Windows Parental Controls (Microsoft)

5xx Server Error

★ 500 Internal Server Error
 503 Service Unavailable
 506 Variant Also Negotiates (Experimental)
 509 Bandwidth Limit Exceeded (Apache)
 598 Network read timeout error

101 Switching Protocols

★ 201 Created
 ★ 204 No Content
 207 Multi-Status (WebDAV)

301 Moved Permanently
 ★ 304 Not Modified
 307 Temporary Redirect

★ 401 Unauthorized
 ★ 404 Not Found
 407 Proxy Authentication Required
 410 Gone
 413 Request Entity Too Large
 416 Requested Range Not Satisfiable
 420 Enhance Your Calm (Twitter)
 424 Failed Dependency (WebDAV)
 428 Precondition Required
 444 No Response (Nginx)
 451 Unavailable For Legal Reasons

501 Not Implemented
 504 Gateway Timeout
 507 Insufficient Storage (WebDAV)
 510 Not Extended
 599 Network connect timeout error

102 Processing (WebDAV)

202 Accepted
 205 Reset Content
 208 Already Reported (WebDAV)

302 Found
 305 Use Proxy
 308 Permanent Redirect (experimental)

402 Payment Required
 405 Method Not Allowed
 408 Request Timeout
 411 Length Required
 414 Request-URI Too Long
 417 Expectation Failed
 422 Unprocessable Entity (WebDAV)
 425 Reserved for WebDAV
 429 Too Many Requests
 449 Retry With (Microsoft)
 499 Client Closed Request (Nginx)

502 Bad Gateway
 505 HTTP Version Not Supported
 508 Loop Detected (WebDAV)
 511 Network Authentication Required

Figure 4. HTTP status codes ([source](#))

The following code snippet creates a RESTful web service using the Node.js and Express framework. A single `/hello/` endpoint responds to GET requests.

```
// simple Express.js RESTful API
'use strict';

// initialize
const
  port = 8888,
  express = require('express'),
  app = express();

// /hello/ GET request
app.get('/hello/:name?', (req, res) =>
  res.json(
    { message: `Hello ${req.params.name || 'world'}!` }
  )
);

// start server
app.listen(port, () =>
  console.log(`Server started on port ${port}`);
);
```

By typing `http://localhost:8888/hello/` in a browser, the following JSON is displayed in response to the GET request:

```
{
  "message": "Hello world!"
}
```

The API also allows a custom name. So, `http://localhost:8888/hello/everyone/` returns:

```
{
  "message": "Hello everyone!"
}
```


2.3.2. SOAP APIs

SOAP (Simple Object Access Protocol) is a standard communication protocol system that permits processes using different operating systems like Linux and Windows to communicate via HTTP and its XML. SOAP was the first to standardise the way applications should use network connections to manage services. It is defined by the World Wide Web Consortium⁶, and its member editors, and it has been leveraged since the late 1990s, the time around which the service-oriented architecture (SOA) took-off. SOAP uses an XML data format to declare its request and response messages, relying on the XML schema and other technologies to enforce the structure of its payloads. Both public and private Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) use SOAP as an interface. Its main function is to define the structure of the messages and methods of communication. It also uses WSDL (Web Services Definition Language) in a machine-readable document to publish a definition of its interface. SOAP-based APIs are designed to create, recover, update and delete records like accounts, passwords, leads, and custom objects. These offers over twenty different kinds of calls make it easy for API developers to maintain their accounts, perform accurate searches and much more. These can then be used with all those languages that support web services. SOAP APIs have the advantage of making web-based protocols such as HTTP and its XML that are already operating with all operating systems. For this reason, developers can easily manipulate web services and get responses without depending on specific programming languages and platforms at all.

SOAP uses the Remote Procedure Call (RPC) pattern, where functions or methods are passed as parameters and return a result. Many RPC solutions prior to SOAP were dependent on specific programming languages or technology stacks. For example, previous RPC implementations often required both sides of the RPC to use the C programming language which predates the modern Internet. Even Java, a programming language of the Internet era, has its own RPC model called Remote Method Invocation (RMI), which was originally coupled to the Java Virtual Machine (JVM). Among the important aspects of SOAP APIs are their independence from programming languages and even the underlying transport protocol. The sender can use C#, for example, while the recipient's stack relies on Java. While these more enterprise-oriented languages are most common with SOAP, there are SOAP implementations in Python, Ruby, and all modern programming languages. A final advantage of SOAP is its extensibility. As a standard, its specification is deliberately limited on constraints. As such, the extensibility model within the SOAP specification allows for customisation.

SOAP comes with strict rules, especially in terms of security, heavy rigid standards and, in some situations, it can be very resource intensive. Except for existing on-premise scenarios, most developers now prefer developing in REST thanks to its lightweight architecture and emphasis on speed and efficiency over SOAP. In order to call a SOAP API, it will be likely needed to include a SOAP library with the programming language used. Although it is possible to make SOAP API calls without SOAP libraries, it is more efficient to work with an abstraction rather than manually crafting the messages. The SOAP messages are verbose, mainly due to reliance on XML. SOAP is intended to be extensible, neutral (able to operate over a range of communication protocols, including HTTP, SMTP, TCP, and more) and independent (it allows for any programming style). The SOAP specification includes:

- The processing model (i.e., how to process a SOAP message).
- The extensibility model (i.e., the SOAP features and modules).
- Protocol binding rules (i.e., how to use SOAP with an underlying protocol such as HTTP).
- Message construct (i.e., how to structure a SOAP message).

It is noteworthy to mention that despite the fact that REST and SOAP are usually considered to be competing standards, it is possible to build a RESTful API by using SOAP protocols.

⁶ <https://www.w3.org/>

2.3.3. RPC

An RPC (Remote Procedure Call) is a remote procedural call protocol. RPC APIs are the oldest and simplest types of API. The goal of an RPC is to allow the client to execute code on a server. The main benefit of RPC APIs is that they make it easier for developers to create applications involving multiple programs or services. XML-RPC uses XML to encode its calls, whereas JSON-RPC uses JSON. As far as those encoding-related RPC APIs are concerned, we may provide the following details:

- **XML-RPC** - This is a protocol that uses a specific XML format to transfer data compared to SOAP that uses a proprietary XML format. By formatting data in XML, simple requests can be made to the server via HTTP. Despite the fact that XML-RPC APIs are easy to develop, they are tightly coupled. To make changes, a new developer would have to go through the XML-RPC's documentation to see how a change in one area could affect another.
- **JSON-RPC** - This is an RPC API coded in JSON. Like XML-RPC, JSON-RPC APIs are easy to develop and implement, but they are tightly coupled as well. This makes these APIs difficult to maintain or update.

Both protocols are simple. A call can contain multiple parameters and expect one result. They have a couple of key features, which require an architecture different to that of REST APIs. They are designed to call methods, whereas REST protocols involve the transfer of documents (resource representations). Or, to put it another way, REST works with resources, whereas RPC is about actions. The URI identifies the server, but contains no information on its parameters. In the case of REST, the URI contains details such as query parameters.

2.3.4. Similarities and differences between the REST and SOAP API architectures

REST has become the preferred choice for public APIs and open source work that allows other developers to connect and easily use the data. Its lighter architecture and allowance for JSON also leads to higher performance that mobile app designers covet. Because of the acceptance of SOAP as a standard protocol, REST has also advanced security features available through SOAP extensions. SOAP APIs forgo performance speed for higher complexity. Many large enterprises build SOAP APIs specifically for these reasons. However, there are many industry best practices for securing REST APIs, as well. Table 2 summarises a number of key similarities and differences between the REST and SOAP API architectural styles.

Table 2. Similarities and differences between the REST and SOAP architectural styles

Similarities between REST and SOAP	Differences between REST and SOAP
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Both SOAP and REST connect to two applications via server-side data that is machine and human-readable. • Both the REST and SOAP APIs typically utilise HTTP protocols and methods (i.e., GET, POST, DELETE). However, they can also use other protocols such as SMTP⁷. • Both architectural styles can understand XML web documentation and can use XML in requests and responses. • Despite their resemblance, there is little relation between providing or consuming SOAP and REST APIs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • REST APIs have no official standards at all. SOAP APIs, on the other hand, have an official standard because they are based on a protocol. • REST APIs use multiple standards like HTTP, JSON, URL, and XML. On the other hand, SOAP APIs are largely based on HTTP and XML. • SOAP is driven by functions, whereas REST is driven by data. • SOAP has strict rules and advanced security features. In the case of REST APIs there are loose guidelines to follow allowing developers to make recommendations easily.

⁷ According to Wikipedia (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Simple_Mail_Transfer_Protocol), SMTP (i.e., Simple Mail Transfer Protocol) is a communication protocol for electronic mail transmission.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SOAP supports only text and numbers, whereas REST supports various types of data (e.g., text, numbers, images, graphs, charts etc.). • Given that REST APIs deploy multiple standards, it takes fewer resources and bandwidth as compared to SOAP that uses XML for the creation of payload and thus results in a large sized file. • The ways these API types expose the business logics are different. The REST API type takes advantage of URL exposure like @path ("/WeatherService"), whereas the SOAP APIs use services interfaces like @WebService. • The SOAP API type defines too many standards and implementation is made in a standard way. In the case of miscommunication from service, the result will be the error. REST APIs, on the other hand, do not emphasise on too many standards. • REST APIs use Web Application Description Language, whereas SOAP APIs use Web Services Description language for describing the functionalities being offered by web services. • REST APIs are more convenient with JavaScript and can be implemented easily as well. SOAP APIs are also convenient with JavaScript but do not support greater implementation. • REST can use XML, but is equally at home with JSON, HTML, and even plain text. By contrast, SOAP APIs require XML as the standard is built upon the format. • SOAP is a standard protocol with strict rules - maintained and fully backed by the W3C consortium. REST is a set of best practices that can be more fluid. • SOAP is built around remote procedure calls and REST is resource-based (i.e., ... getUser(23) vs /user/23). • Despite the fact that some organisations support both SOAP and REST APIs, the existing differences tend to impact the REST API design. By being the most flexible one, REST tends to meet the needs of the standards-focused SOAP API.
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3. The EURAKNOS Application Programming Interface

3.1. Technologies used for the creation of the EURAKNOS Application Programming Interface

The EURAKNOS e-KRP system architecture which serves as the infrastructure and solid base of the API is thoroughly explained and presented in Deliverable 4.3 (“e-KRP documentation and guide”)⁸. In this section, a brief reference to some basic technology components is made to serve as a reminder and an introduction to the documentation of the API.

Drupal

Drupal⁹ is a free and open-source web content management framework developed in PHP and distributed under the GNU General Public License¹⁰. Drupal provides a back-end framework for at least 12% of the top 10,000 websites worldwide ranging from personal blogs to corporate, political, and government websites. Drupal is also used for knowledge management and for business collaboration. Drupal has great standard features like easy content authoring, reliable performance, and excellent security features. It is very flexible, modular and allows developers build versatile, structured content that dynamic web experiences need.

Contenta CMS

The Contenta¹¹ Content Management System (CMS)¹² is a decoupled, API-driven Drupal distribution built using the JSON API. Contenta helps offer modern, out-of-the-box capabilities with the JSON API. Whether the case is a single application development or a multi-channel publishing, Contenta is considered to be a Create Once, Publish Everywhere CMS. It is built by the same community initiative promoting the JSON API module. It provides many preconfigured options including customisation to default endpoints. It also provides Simple OAuth to set up decoupled authentication with the product’s frontend consumer and the API backend.

Initially, the EURAKNOS API has been considered to be developed as a Drupal API proof-of-concept. Over the course of the overlapping EUREKA project, this codebase was further developed into a more elaborate solution. Due to these further developments not all of which fit the initial API, and other technical reasons (e.g., the latest release of the third party DSpace repository requiring more elaborate security and configuration), rather than forking an older commit of the existing (now EUREKA) repository, the decision was made to instead reimplement the same solution in the already present ETL (“Extract, Transform and Load”) service. This EURAKNOS implementation differs in that it is now realised in a Java spring boot service, but functionality and design are identical.

3.2. Documentation of the EURAKNOS Application Programming Interface

In general terms, the documentation of an API provides accounts of the API services, and how to use those services, aiming to cover any client need. The API documentation is crucial for the development and maintenance of applications using the API. Good documentation accelerates development and consumption, and reduces the money and time that would otherwise be spent in order to respond to support calls. Documentation is part of the overall user experience and is one of the major factors that contribute to the increased API growth and usage.

⁸ Panoutsopoulos et al. (2021). e-KRP documentation and guide. EURAKNOS – Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs towards a European Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Open Source System Deliverable 4.3 – WP4

⁹ <https://www.drupal.org/>

¹⁰ <https://www.gnu.org/licenses/gpl-3.0.html>

¹¹ <http://www.contentacms.org/>

¹² The interested reader may refer to https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Content_management_system in order to access further information about what a Content Management System (CMS).

It is traditionally found in documentation files but can also be found in social media such as blogs, fora, and Q&A websites. In the interest of clarity, API documentation may include a description of classes and methods in the API as well as “*typical usage scenarios, code snippets, design rationale, performance discussions, and contracts*”. Yet, for reasons of simplicity, the implementation details of the API services are usually omitted.

Restrictions and limitations on how the API can be used are also covered in the documentation. For instance, the documentation of an API function could note that its parameters cannot be null or that the function itself is not thread safe. An API documentation needs to be comprehensive; therefore, the documentation creators should keep the documentation updated and the interested users should read it carefully. It is also possible to generate API documentation in a data-driven manner. By observing many programs that use a given API, it is possible to infer the typical usage as well the required contracts and directives. Then, templates can be used to generate natural language from the mined data. API documentation can be enriched with metadata information which can be used by the compiler, tools, and by the run-time environment to implement custom behaviors or custom handling.

For the EURAKNOS API documentation, two very popular API documentation tools have been used.

Swagger

Swagger¹³ is an Interface Description Language for describing RESTful APIs expressed using JSON. It is used together with a set of open-source software tools to design, build, document, and use RESTful web services. Swagger includes automated documentation, code generation (into many programming languages), and test-case generation. The Swagger specification, which was renamed to the OpenAPI Specification (OAS), has become the standard for defining RESTful APIs.

Documentation from the generated contact would mean adding meaningful, understandable information that end users can use to achieve API success. OAS allows us to describe important details, including:

- **Media types** - Media type is a format of a request or response body data. Web service operations can accept and return data in different formats, the most common being JSON, XML and images.
- **Endpoints/Resources** - These may have an optional short summary and a longer description for documentation purposes. This information is supposed to be relevant to all operations in this endpoint. Description can be multi-line and supports Markdown (CommonMark) for rich text representation.
- **Request bodies** - Request bodies are typically used with “create” and “update” operations (POST, PUT, PATCH). For example, when creating a resource using POST or PUT, the request body usually contains the representation of the resource to be created.
- **Responses** - An API definition needs to specify the responses for all API operations. Each operation must have at least one response defined, usually a successful response. A response is defined by its HTTP status code and the data returned in the response body and/or headers.
- **Authentication** - Authentication is described by using the security definitions and security keywords. Security definitions are used to define all authentication types supported by the API; then, security is also applied for specific authentication types to the whole API or individual operations.
- **Examples** - Examples can be added to parameters, properties and objects to make OpenAPI specification of a web service clearer. Examples can be read by tools and libraries that process the API in some way.

¹³ <https://swagger.io/>

Redoc

Redoc¹⁴ is an open-source tool that generates API documentation from OpenAPI specifications. It's one of the most powerful free docs tools in the industry producing clean, customisable documentation with an attractive three-panel design. With support for Markdown, it allows to write and style descriptions with ease. In practice, Redoc generates documentation by consuming an OpenAPI specification within the browser, eliminating the need for servers. ReDoc is done in responsive three-panel design. The left panel contains a scroll-synchronized reference menu. The middle panel contains endpoints/methods documentation. The right panel contains various samples such as request samples, response samples, and code samples (via vendor extensions). All method responses are listed under the method definition and are colored according to the response code. Response also contains header and payload documentations.

3.3. Example use cases for the EURAKNOS API

EURAKNOS API and its documentation can be found at <https://api.upload.mvp.euraknos.cf/swagger-ui/index.html#/>. It is live and will be dynamically updated based on the updates provided in the context of the EUREKA project¹⁵. The updates may refer to new configuration on any part of the API (authentication, authorisation, ways of retrieving information, remodeling or availability of specific knowledge objects, etc.). Any update in the API documentation, will be documented in the corresponding deliverables of EUREKA project since this API will also be an integral part of the EUREKA FarmBook system's architecture.

In order to access the API, the interested parties need to be registered users. Test accounts have been created for testing purposes to ensure the API is fully functional before its final release. All interested parties who need to access the API can request to be provided with credentials through test accounts, from the coordinating team. The registration process is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Users have to be registered in order to access the API and make some calls.

¹⁴ <https://redoc.ly/>

¹⁵ <https://www.h2020eureka.eu/>

After acquiring the credentials it is a very simple process to start consuming the API. All calls are already integrated in the interface and the user only needs to click on the “Execute” button in order to make a call. When further attributes are required (object ID, number of pages to be retrieved) to customise the API call, they can be easily inserted as values in the form fields. The response is presented in a very detailed manner with simple explanatory text signifying the request details, the response details and different code messages ensuring that all interested parties, who have the slightest familiarisation with an API structure, are able to use it instantly. All responses can be also downloaded in a JSON format by clicking on the “Download” button.

The screenshot displays a web interface for API testing. It shows a curl command, the request URL, and a successful server response (200 OK). The response body is a JSON object containing metadata and provenance information. The response headers include cache-control, connection, content-type, date, expires, keep-alive, pragma, server, transfer-encoding, vary, x-content-type-options, x-frame-options, and x-xss-protection. A list of response codes is also shown, including 200 (OK), 401 (Unauthorized), 403 (Forbidden), and 404 (Not Found).

```
curl -X GET "https://api.upload.mvp.euraknos.cf/api/knowledgeobject/" -H "accept: */*"

Request URL
https://api.upload.mvp.euraknos.cf/api/knowledgeobject/

Server response
Code 200 Details
Response body
{
  "id": "0021f020-e2cd-4de0-8d69-bb2df24d355f",
  "uuid": "0021f020-e2cd-4de0-8d69-bb2df24d355f",
  "name": null,
  "handle": "123456789/688",
  "metadata": {
    "dc.date.accessioned": [
      {
        "value": "2021-05-31T17:34:25Z",
        "language": null,
        "authority": null,
        "confidence": -1,
        "place": 0
      }
    ],
    "dc.date.available": [
      {
        "value": "2021-05-31T17:34:25Z",
        "language": null,
        "authority": null,
        "confidence": -1,
        "place": 0
      }
    ],
    "dc.description.provenance": [

```

```
cache-control: no-cache-no-store-max-age=0must-revalidate
connection: Keep-Alive
content-type: application/json
date: Tue14 Sep 2021 06:05:04 GMT
expires: 0
keep-alive: timeout=5max=100
pragma: no-cache
server: Apache/2.4.29 (Ubuntu)
transfer-encoding: chunked
vary: Origin,Access-Control-Request-Method,Access-Control-Request-Headers
x-content-type-options: nosniff
x-frame-options: DENY
x-xss-protection: 1; mode=block

Responses
Code 200 Description
OK
Example Value | Model
[
  {}
]
Code 401 Description
Unauthorized
Code 403 Description
Forbidden
Code 404 Description
Not Found
```

Figure 6. The API follows a very familiar structure regarding the request call and the response

In the following figures we present some useful examples or common use cases showcasing how the interested parties can access and retrieve information from the e-KRP. Figure 7 below shows the call related to the request to retrieve one specific data object. To achieve this, the user must know the data object’s uuid attribute in order to pass it as a parameter to the request.

The screenshot shows a REST client interface with the following details:

- Method:** GET
- URL:** /api/knowledgeobject/{id} getKnowledgeObject
- Parameters:** id (required, string, path) with value 0021f028-e2cd-4de0-8d69-bb2df24d355f
- Request:** curl -X GET "https://api.upload.mvp.euraknos.cf/api/knowledgeobject/0021f028-e2cd-4de0-8d69-bb2df24d355f" -H "accept: */*"
- Response Code:** 200
- Response Body (JSON):**

```
{
  "id": "0021f028-e2cd-4de0-8d69-bb2df24d355f",
  "uuid": "0021f028-e2cd-4de0-8d69-bb2df24d355f",
  "name": null,
  "handle": "123456789/688",
  "metadata": {
    "dc.date.accessioned": {
      "value": "2021-05-31T17:34:25Z",
      "language": null,
      "authority": null,
      "confidence": -1,
      "place": 0
    },
    "dc.date.available": {
      "value": "2021-05-31T17:34:25Z",
      "language": null,
      "authority": null,
      "confidence": -1,
      "place": 0
    },
    "dc.description.provenance": {
      "value": "Made available in DSpace on 2021-05-31T17:34:25Z (GMT). No. of bitstreams: 1\nPractical_aspects_relat...to_agroforestry_implementation_in_Flanders_PA_AFINET_EN.pdf: 28884 bytes, checksum: acac4f9ec358e4f39572d1b9c7f0d96 (MD5);",
      "language": "en",
      "authority": null,
      "confidence": -1,
      "place": 0
    },
    "dc.identifier.uri": {
      "value": "http://dspace-angular:4800/handle/123456789/688",
      "language": null,
      "authority": null,
      "confidence": -1,
      "place": 0
    },
    "knowledgeobject.checksum": {
      "value": "acac4f9ec358e4f39572d1b9c7f0d96",
      "language": "",
      "authority": null,
      "confidence": -1,
      "place": 0
    },
    "knowledgeobject.content.language": {
      "value": "English",
      "language": "",
      "authority": null,
      "confidence": -1,
      "place": 0
    },
    "knowledgeobject.content.location": {
      "value": "N.A.",
      "language": "",
      "authority": null,
      "confidence": -1,
      "place": 0
    },
    "knowledgeobject.creator": {
      "value": "AFINET",
      "language": "",
      "authority": null,
      "confidence": -1,
      "place": 0
    },
    "knowledgeobject.datecreated": {
      "value": "N.A.",
      "language": "",
      "authority": null,
      "confidence": -1,
      "place": 0
    },
    "knowledgeobject.description": {
      "value": "A practice abstract for practical aspects related to agroforestry implementation in Flanders",
      "language": "",
      "authority": null,
      "confidence": -1,
      "place": 0
    },
    "knowledgeobject.fileformat": {
      "value": "pdf",
      "language": "",
      "authority": null,
      "confidence": -1,
      "place": 0
    },
    "knowledgeobject.filesize": {
      "value": "29 KB",
      "language": "",
      "authority": null,
      "confidence": -1,
      "place": 0
    },
    "knowledgeobject.keywords": {
      "value": "farming practice; climate and climate change; animal husbandry and welfare; land-scope; land management; pests and disease control; soil management and functionality; forestry farming; forestry competitiveness and diversification; supply chain marketing and consumption",
      "language": "",
      "authority": null,
      "confidence": -1,
      "place": 0
    },
    "knowledgeobject.license": {
      "value": "N.A.",
      "language": "",
      "authority": null,
      "confidence": -1,
      "place": 0
    },
    "knowledgeobject.purpose": {
      "value": "dissemination; education/training",
      "language": "",
      "authority": null,
      "confidence": -1,
      "place": 0
    },
    "knowledgeobject.thematicnetwork.acronym": {
      "value": "AFINET",
      "language": "",
      "authority": null,
      "confidence": -1,
      "place": 0
    },
    "knowledgeobject.thematicnetwork.domain": {
      "value": "Forestry",
      "language": "",
      "authority": null,
      "confidence": -1,
      "place": 0
    },
    "knowledgeobject.thematicnetwork.fullname": {
      "value": "Agroforestry Innovation Networks",
      "language": "",
      "authority": null,
      "confidence": -1,
      "place": 0
    },
    "knowledgeobject.thematicnetwork.url": {
      "value": "https://euraf.isa.utl.pt/afinet",
      "language": "",
      "authority": null,
      "confidence": -1,
      "place": 0
    },
    "knowledgeobject.title": {
      "value": "Practical aspects related to agroforestry implementation in Flanders",
      "language": "",
      "authority": null,
      "confidence": -1,
      "place": 0
    },
    "knowledgeobject.topic": {
      "value": "forestry practices; animal husbandry and welfare practices",
      "language": "",
      "authority": null,
      "confidence": -1,
      "place": 0
    },
    "knowledgeobject.type": {
      "value": "Practice abstract",
      "language": "",
      "authority": null,
      "confidence": -1,
      "place": 0
    },
    "knowledgeobject.url": {
      "value": "https://ac.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/find-connect/projects/afinet-red-abstract?language=-1",
      "language": "",
      "authority": null,
      "confidence": -1,
      "place": 0
    },
    "inarchive": true,
    "discoverable": true,
    "withdrawn": false,
    "lastmodified": "2021-05-31T17:34:25.564+0000",
    "type": "item",
    "links": {
      "bundles": {
        "href": "http://dspace:8080/server/api/core/items/0021f028-e2cd-4de0-8d69-bb2df24d355f/mappedCollections",
        "owningCollection": {
          "href": "http://dspace:8080/server/api/core/items/0021f028-e2cd-4de0-8d69-bb2df24d355f/owningCollection",
          "relationships": {
            "href": "http://dspace:8080/server/api/core/items/0021f028-e2cd-4de0-8d69-bb2df24d355f/ver-..."
          }
        }
      }
    }
  }
}
```
- Response Headers:**

```
Cache-Control: no-cache, no-store, max-age=0, must-revalidate
Connection: keep-alive
Content-Encoding: gzip
Content-Length: 1125
Content-Type: text/plain; charset=UTF-8
Date: Tue, 14 Sep 2021 06:11:42 GMT
Expires: 0
Keep-Alive: timeout=5, max=100
Pragma: no-cache
Server: Apache/2.4.29 (Ubuntu)
Vary: Origin, Accept-Encoding, Access-Control-Request-Method, Access-Control-Request-Headers
X-Content-Type-Options: nosniff
X-Frame-Options: DENY
X-XSS-Protection: 1; mode=block
```

Figure 7. Retrieving a specific knowledge object. In this case a uuid is required in order to target on the knowledge object.

As illustrated in the following example, a specific object, available from the 4D4F Thematic Network, has been selected and retrieved. The data object is a Practice Abstract also available from the database of EIP-AGRI. We have highlighted the most important attributes describing the data object. Additional metadata are added to the JSON instance automatically through the uploading process, whereas some are left blank as optional. The response for each of the data objects contains all the required metadata listed and thoroughly described in Deliverable 4.3 “e-KRP Documentation and guide” (and also shown in Figure 8 below).

```
{
  "id": "03885532-443d-41d1-8201-ef38eab2d681",
  "uuid": "03885532-443d-41d1-8201-ef38eab2d681",
  "name": null,
  "handle": "123456789/652",
  "metadata": {
    "dc.date.accessioned": [
      {
        "value": "2021-05-31T17:31:24Z",
```



```

    "language": null,
    "authority": null,
    "confidence": -1,
    "place": 0
  }
],
"dc.date.available": [
  {
    "value": "2021-05-31T17:31:24Z",
    "language": null,
    "authority": null,
    "confidence": -1,
    "place": 0
  }
],
"dc.description.provenance": [
  {
    "value": "Made available in DSpace on 2021-05-31T17:31:24Z (GMT). No. of bitstreams:
1\nManaging_fresh_grass_intake_in_the_pasture_PA_4D4F_EN.pdf: 28406 bytes, checksum:
15a6a6a3ff5d6de584c514a430a92dc7 (MD5)",
    "language": "en",
    "authority": null,
    "confidence": -1,
    "place": 0
  }
],
"dc.identifier.uri": [
  {
    "value": "http://dspace-angular:4000/handle/123456789/652",
    "language": null,
    "authority": null,
    "confidence": -1,
    "place": 0
  }
],
"knowledgeobject.checksum": [
  {
    "value": "15a6a6a3ff5d6de584c514a430a92dc7",
    "language": "",
    "authority": null,
    "confidence": -1,
    "place": 0
  }
],
"knowledgeobject.content.language": [
  {
    "value": "English",
    "language": "",
    "authority": null,
    "confidence": -1,
    "place": 0
  }
],
"knowledgeobject.content.location": [
  {
    "value": "N.A.",
    "language": "",
    "authority": null,
    "confidence": -1,
    "place": 0
  }
],
"knowledgeobject.creator": [

```



```

{
  "value": "4D4F",
  "language": "",
  "authority": null,
  "confidence": -1,
  "place": 0
}
],
"knowledgeobject.datecreated": [
{
  "value": "N.A.",
  "language": "",
  "authority": null,
  "confidence": -1,
  "place": 0
}
],
"knowledgeobject.dateextracted": [
{
  "value": "N.A.",
  "language": "",
  "authority": null,
  "confidence": -1,
  "place": 0
}
],
"knowledgeobject.description": [
{
  "value": "A practice abstract for Managing fresh grass intake in the pasture.",
  "language": "",
  "authority": null,
  "confidence": -1,
  "place": 0
}
],
"knowledgeobject.fileformat": [
{
  "value": "pdf",
  "language": "",
  "authority": null,
  "confidence": -1,
  "place": 0
}
],
"knowledgeobject.filesize": [
{
  "value": "28 KB",
  "language": "",
  "authority": null,
  "confidence": -1,
  "place": 0
}
],
"knowledgeobject.keywords": [
{
  "value": "agricultural production system; farming practice; farming equipment and machinery; animal husbandry and welfare; farming and forestry competitiveness; farming and forestry diversification; best practice; data-driven agriculture; knowledge exchange; dairy farming",
  "language": "",
  "authority": null,
  "confidence": -1,
  "place": 0
}
]

```

```

],
"knowledgeobject.license": [
  {
    "value": "N.A.",
    "language": "",
    "authority": null,
    "confidence": -1,
    "place": 0
  }
],
"knowledgeobject.purpose": [
  {
    "value": "dissemination; education/training",
    "language": "",
    "authority": null,
    "confidence": -1,
    "place": 0
  }
],
"knowledgeobject.thematicnetwork.acronym": [
  {
    "value": "4D4F",
    "language": "",
    "authority": null,
    "confidence": -1,
    "place": 0
  }
],
"knowledgeobject.thematicnetwork.domain": [
  {
    "value": "Animal Husbandry and Welfare",
    "language": "",
    "authority": null,
    "confidence": -1,
    "place": 0
  }
],
"knowledgeobject.thematicnetwork.fullname": [
  {
    "value": "Data Driven Dairy Decisions 4 Farmers",
    "language": "",
    "authority": null,
    "confidence": -1,
    "place": 0
  }
],
"knowledgeobject.thematicnetwork.url": [
  {
    "value": "http://www.4d4f.eu/",
    "language": "",
    "authority": null,
    "confidence": -1,
    "place": 0
  }
],
"knowledgeobject.title": [
  {
    "value": "Managing fresh grass intake in the pasture",
    "language": "",
    "authority": null,
    "confidence": -1,
    "place": 0
  }
]

```

```

],
"knowledgeobject.topic": [
  {
    "value": "forestry practices; animal husbandry and welfare practices; crop farming practices",
    "language": "",
    "authority": null,
    "confidence": -1,
    "place": 0
  }
],
"knowledgeobject.type": [
  {
    "value": "Practice abstract",
    "language": "",
    "authority": null,
    "confidence": -1,
    "place": 0
  }
],
"knowledgeobject.url": [
  {
    "value": "https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/find-connect/projects/4d4f-data-driven-dairy-decisions-farmers",
    "language": "",
    "authority": null,
    "confidence": -1,
    "place": 0
  }
]
],
"inArchive": true,
"discoverable": true,
"withdrawn": false,
"lastModified": "2021-05-31T17:31:24.889+0000",
"type": "item",
"_links": {
  "bundles": {
    "href": "http://dspace:8080/server/api/core/items/03885532-443d-41d1-8201-ef38eab2d681/bundles"
  },
  "mappedCollections": {
    "href": "http://dspace:8080/server/api/core/items/03885532-443d-41d1-8201-ef38eab2d681/mappedCollections"
  },
  "owningCollection": {
    "href": "http://dspace:8080/server/api/core/items/03885532-443d-41d1-8201-ef38eab2d681/owningCollection"
  },
  "relationships": {
    "href": "http://dspace:8080/server/api/core/items/03885532-443d-41d1-8201-ef38eab2d681/relationships"
  },
  "version": {
    "href": "http://dspace:8080/server/api/core/items/03885532-443d-41d1-8201-ef38eab2d681/version"
  },
  "templateItemOf": {
    "href": "http://dspace:8080/server/api/core/items/03885532-443d-41d1-8201-ef38eab2d681/templateItemOf"
  },
  "self": {
    "href": "http://dspace:8080/server/api/core/items/03885532-443d-41d1-8201-ef38eab2d681"
  }
}
}
}

```


#	Metadata property	Definition	Matching property from external ontology	Property URI
1	title	The title of the content available from the data object.	no relevant property from external vocabulary	
2	description	A short textual description of what the content of the data object is about.	schema:description	http://schema.org/description
3	keywords	Keywords or tags used to describe the content of the data object.	schema:keywords	http://schema.org/keywords
4	creator	The creator/author of the data object.	schema:creator	http://schema.org/creator
5	inLanguage	The language in which the content of the data object is available.	no relevant property from external vocabulary	
6	contentLocation	The location depicted or described in the content.	schema:contentLocation	http://schema.org/contentLocation
7	fileUrl	The URL allowing to download the data object.	schema:url	http://schema.org/url
8	topic	The topic addressed in the content of a data object.	foaf:topic	http://xmlns.com/foaf/0.1/topic
9	purpose	The purpose for which the data object has been created.	schema:potentialAction	http://schema.org/potentialAction
10	fileFormat	The file type of the data object.	dct:format	http://purl.org/dc/terms/format
11	type	The type property relates to what the content of the data object is about. ⁷¹	no relevant property from external vocabulary	
12	fileSize	The size of the file/package. In the absence of a unit, KB is assumed.	schema:fileSize	http://schema.org/fileSize
13	fileChecksum	A sequence of characters used to check a data object for errors.	no relevant property from external vocabulary	
14	dateCreated	The date on which a data object was created.	schema:dateCreated	https://schema.org/dateCreated
15	license	A license document that applies to this content, typically indicated by URL.	schema:license	http://schema.org/license
16	ThematicNetwork Acronym	The acronym of the Thematic Network (e.g., AFINET).	schema:alternateName	http://schema.org/alternateName
17	ThematicNetwork FullName	The full name of the Thematic Network (e.g., Agroforestry Innovation Networks).	schema:name	http://schema.org/name
18	ThematicNetwork Url	The URL of the Thematic Network or the URL directing to the TN-related record in the CORDIS database (in the case that the TN's URL is dead).	schema:url	http://schema.org/url
19	ThematicNetwork Domain	The agricultural sector (i.e., Crop farming, Livestock, or Forestry) to which the Thematic Network relates.	no relevant property from external vocabulary	

Figure 8. The metadata that are used to describe the data objects in the EURAKNOS e-KRP

Figure 9 below illustrates the API call about the request for a list of all the data objects available from the e-KRP. The user is able to specify the number of pages to be created when viewing the list of results. The response can be downloaded in Ja SON format in order to be used externally for any purposes that may suit the user’s needs.

The screenshot shows an API client interface for a GET request to `/api/knowledgeobject/`. The parameters section includes:

- `page`: `integer($int32)page` (query) with a value of `page - page`
- `size`: `integer($int32)size` (query) with a value of `size - size`

The response section shows a 200 status code and a JSON response body:

```

{
  "id": "0021f020-e2cd-4de0-8d69-bb2df24d355f",
  "uuid": "0021f020-e2cd-4de0-8d69-bb2df24d355f",
  "name": null,
  "handle": "123456789/688",
  "metadata": {
    "dc.date.accessioned": [
      {
        "value": "2021-05-31T17:34:25Z",
        "Language": null,
        "authority": null,
        "confidence": -1,
        "place": 0
      }
    ],
    "dc.date.available": [
      {
        "value": "2021-05-31T17:34:25Z",
        "Language": null,
        "authority": null,
        "confidence": -1,
        "place": 0
      }
    ],
    "dc.description.provenance": [

```

Figure 9. Retrieving a list of data objects. The configuration of the request (meaning the parameters) is shown in the middle of the figure and the downloadable response of the request on the bottom part of the figure.

Figure 10 shows the API call related to the deletion of a specific data object from the e-KRP. To achieve this, the user must know the specific data object’s uuid attribute in order to pass it as a parameter to the request.

DELETE /api/knowledgeobject/{id} deleteKnowledgeObject

Parameters Cancel

Name	Description
id * required string (path)	id

0021f028-e2cd-4de0-8d69-bb2df24d355f

Execute

Responses Response content type: */*

Code	Description
200	OK
204	No Content
401	Unauthorized
403	Forbidden

```

{
  "body": {},
  "statusCode": "ACCEPTED",
  "statusCodeValue": 0
}

```

Figure 10. Deleting a specific knowledge object. In this case a uuid is required in order to target on the knowledge object

4. Conclusions and next steps

The present deliverable report has been concerned with the provision of the documentation of the API built in EURAKNOS in order to allow third-party entities (i.e., human and/or machine agents) to access and consume the data available from the EURAKNOS repository. It presents the technologies that have been used for its development and the calls used for performing basic operations. Such operations are the retrieval and deletion of an existing data object. The purpose of this mechanism is to facilitate and enable the re-use of the data objects available from the EURAKNOS repository. To achieve this, a number of API-related dissemination activities are envisioned. More specifically, there is a number of events that have been scheduled to take place, in the context of the EURAKNOS project, in February 2021. These events are the EURAKNOS “Raiders of the potentially lost Agricultural Knowledge” event that will be held on the 5th of February 2021 and the final conference of EURAKNOS that has been scheduled to take place on the 26th of February. Within the same context, the EUREKA WP1 Central meeting of the Knowledge Innovation Panel (scheduled for the 16th of February, 2021) can also be considered. The intention of holding activities for the dissemination of the API in these events is to make it known to a wide audience who are considered to be the main users of the EURAKNOS platform. The API development will continue in the context of the EUREKA project, which has a broader scope than that of EURAKNOS in regard to the type of projects and data objects. In this context, some more, additional features are intended to be considered. Such an additional feature could be the provision of a SPARQL¹⁶ endpoint allowing to access data object – related metadata information available in the form of RDF triples¹⁷.

¹⁶ Information and details about what SPARQL is can be accessed at <https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf-sparql-query/>.

¹⁷ Information and details about what RDF is can be accessed at <https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf-primer/>.

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